

IMPROVED MACHINE FOR SPREADING AND COMPACTING ROAD CONSTRUCTION MATERIALS.

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The road construction work is carried out in phases based on the project. Design is an integral part of road construction and reconstruction. In order to save material costs for road construction, it is necessary to qualitatively justify cost-effectiveness in the design process. Modern road design represents a compromise between a number of controversial requirements, that is, minimum construction work, the highest efficiency and safety in road transport, the use of inexpensive land and the protection of the environment. These requirements can be met by sensible solutions with maximum design options. The scientific and technical level of design must be improved.

Roads are actively affected by many natural-climatic factors (snow drifting, wetting by precipitation, surface water and groundwater, etc.). These characteristics of roads need to be taken into account when designing.

In the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev dated 27 November 2018 PQ-4035 - "Design and road works on the basis of advanced development of road infrastructure of the country, introduction of advanced technologies and best foreign practices to further improve its quality, as well as comprehensive improvement of public administration system in road construction in inseparable connection with the Action Strategy on five priority areas of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021:

1. The following priorities for road construction and operation in the Republic of Uzbekistan should be outlined:

The first is the introduction of modern, innovative technologies and materials used in road construction, ensuring globally recognised standards and best practice in road design and construction, improving the quality and durability of roads;

Secondly, to increase the efficiency of financial resources used in road construction, expand the scope of attracting preferential credit lines from international financial institutions and foreign banking institutions in the implementation of road construction and reconstruction projects of international and national importance. and also, a broader incentive for private investment in public road construction;

Thirdly, first of all, the active assimilation and effective implementation of best foreign experience and practice in road construction by attracting major contracting organisations with leading foreign companies and highly qualified specialists to the country's regions.;

Fourth, to improve the quality of road maintenance work by actively equipping road maintenance enterprises with modern road construction and repair equipment, including through leasing, and by introducing effective technologies for organising their work;

Fifth, the creation of joint ventures for the production of modern construction materials and special road-building machinery for road construction with the participation of leading foreign companies in the country's territories, and the opening of service centres to service them in the future;

Sixth, to radically improve the system of training, retraining and professional development for road construction staff, including in cooperation with foreign educational institutions and centres related to the sector, as well as the provision of internships for local specialists in leading foreign road construction companies. organisation of programmes.

Considering the above, it should be noted that improvements in road construction machines are indicative of the student of the modern age..

1 - picture. General view of the improved machine for spreading and compacting road construction materials

With the improved machine for spreading and compacting road construction materials, efficiency will be higher than with existing machines. The reason is that this machine can spread and compact road construction materials at the same time. This, in turn, leads to increased productivity.

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